

**THE POTENTIAL FOR PEROVSKITE SOLAR PANEL
PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: Nowadays, as the global population continues to grow, the demand for electrical energy is also increasing. In addition, the depletion of non-renewable resources and associated environmental issues have led to complications in conventional methods of electricity generation. As a result, there is a growing need for alternative energy sources. One of the most widespread alternatives is solar energy. This article explores a potential solution to the problems associated with conventional mono-crystalline silicon solar panels by replacing traditional materials with substances that have a perovskite structure in solar panel design.

Keywords: Solar cells, renewable energy, mono-crystalline silicon, perovskite.

Introduction

In recent years, the rapid growth of the global population and the expansion of economic activity have led to an unprecedented increase in the demand for energy. According to the United Nations, the world population surpassed 8 billion in 2023 and is expected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050. As the population grows, so too does electricity consumption, driven by improvements in living standards, industrial production, transportation usage, and overall quality of life. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) report published in 2022, global demand for electricity is increasing by an average of 2.4% annually [3–5].

At this pace, the production, supply, and consumption of energy are contributing to the rapid depletion of traditional energy sources such as coal, oil, and natural gas. Furthermore, the combustion of these fossil fuels releases significant amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the atmosphere, exacerbating global warming, climate change, melting glaciers, rising sea levels, droughts, and other environmental threats. For instance, a joint report by NASA and the United Nations on climate change notes that since the Industrial Revolution, the Earth's average temperature has risen by approximately 1.1°C—and this trend is continuing [6–8].

These pressing issues are compelling humanity to seek out new, environmentally friendly, sustainable, and renewable energy sources. Such sources are referred to as “alternative energy” or “renewable energy.” These types of energy sources have the unique characteristic of being naturally replenished, making them virtually inexhaustible and environmentally benign. Examples of renewable energy include solar radiation, wind movement, water flow, geothermal heat, and biochemical fuels, which constitute the main types of alternative energy [9–11].

According to the BP Statistical Review of World Energy, renewable energy currently accounts for 31.4% of the total global energy production, with the following distribution illustrated below (Figure 1) [1].

Figure 1. World electricity consumption

Solar energy accounts for approximately 6% of the total electricity generated worldwide and about 19% of all renewable energy. As of 2023, the annual electricity generation capacity from solar energy reached approximately 1,631 TWh. By 2024, this figure had increased to around 2,132 TWh, representing a 30% growth compared to the previous year [2].

Everyday sun sends out tremendous amount of energy in the form of heat and radiations called solar energy. Solar energy is a limitless source of energy which is available at no cost. The major benefit of solar energy over other conventional power generators is that the sunlight can be directly harvested into solar energy with the use of small and tiny photovoltaic (PV) solar cells. The Sun is assumed as a big spherical gaseous cloud made up of hydrogen and helium atoms. This big spherical gaseous cloud is mainly composed of several hydrogen nuclear combining to form helium energy with the emission of energy from the fusion of the hydrogen nuclei in inner core of the Sun via nuclear fusion (Figure 2) [12-15].

Figure 2. Nuclear fusion of hydrogen

During this process of fusion, four hydrogen atoms combine to form one helium atom with a loss of mass which is radiated as thermal energy [1] [4] - [5] . This radiant energy produced by fusion reactions is free from any pollutant, gases, or other reaction by-product. This is why it is the major driving force of all the clean energy technology, in view of the climatic disturbance caused by the emission of carbon from the fossil fuels deposits. One of the biggest advantages of solar energy is that it is free reachable to common people and available in abundant supply compared to that of the price of various fossil fuels and oils in the past decade [1] - [7] . Moreover, solar energy requires considerably lower manpower expenses over conventional energy production technology [16].

There have been an enormous amount of research activities to harvest the Sun's energy effectively by developing solar cells/panels with high conversion efficiencies. The photovoltaic conversion efficiency is referred to the efficiency of solar PV modules, and is defined as the fraction of Sun's energy that can be converted into electricity. Solar panels are a huge collection of tiny solar cells arranged in a definite geometrical shape to produce a given amount of power supply. The storage of solar power is still has not been achieved successfully. Currently the radiation efficiency of solar panel is up to 22-23.7%. There are many solar photovoltaic batteries available which are usually more expensive and bulky. These are more suitable for small scale or household solar needs compared to large solar plants [17-18].

The working mechanism of solar cells is based on the three factors: Adsorption of light in order to generate the charge carriers, holes (p-type) and electrons (n-type). Separation of charge carriers, and the collection of charge carriers at the respective electrodes establishing the potential difference across the p-n junction. The generation of voltage difference noticed at the p-n junction of the cell in response to visible radiation is utilized to do the work (figure 3).

Figure 3. Layers of typical solar cells

The photovoltaic (PV) effect was first observed by Alexandre-Edmond Becquerel in 1839. Subsequently, in 1946 the first modern solar cell made of silicon was invented by Russel Ohl . Earlier photovoltaic solar cells are thin silicon wafers that transform sunlight energy into electrical power [19]. The modern photovoltaic technology are made up of several layers, each designed to perform a specific function in converting sunlight into electricity.

Glass cover – protective layer. It is aimed to protect the solar cell from environmental damage such as rain and dust. This layer is usually made of tempered glass. Anti-reflective coating – this layer minimizes the reflection of sunlight. Without this layer much of the light would bounce off the cell surface and be wasted. Front contact – metallic grid. It collects electrons generated by the cell and transports them to the external circuit. N-type semiconductor layer contains extra electrons (negative charge carriers). This is the top layer of the p-n junction where light hits first. P-N Junction - core area where electricity is generated. Light energy excites electrons, causing them to move from the p-side to the n-side, creating a voltage difference. The electric field at the junction helps separate the charge carriers. P-type semiconductor layer contains "holes" or missing electrons (positive charge carriers). This layer is located under the p-n junction. Back Contact – a metal layer completes the electrical circuit by allowing electrons to return to the cell. It may be made of aluminium [20-21].

In this arrangement of the structure, when a photon of sufficient energy impinges on the p-type and n-type junction, an electron is ejected by gaining energy from the striking photon and moves from one layer to another. This creates an electron and a hole in the process and by this process electrical power is generated. The various types of materials applied for photovoltaic solar cells includes mainly in the form of silicon (figure 4) [22].

Figure 4. The various types of materials applied for photovoltaic solar cells

Currently, monocrystalline silicon is the most widely used material in solar panel manufacturing. Over the past five years, approximately 70% of all solar panels produced have been based on monocrystalline technology.

The use of monocrystalline silicon in solar cell technology dates back to 1954, when researchers at Bell Labs developed the first practical photovoltaic cell using a single-crystal silicon wafer. These early solar cells achieved an efficiency of around 6% and were primarily utilized in space applications, where high performance and reliability were essential. During the 1980s and 1990s, the focus shifted toward commercial viability, with improvements in the Czochralski process leading to higher-quality silicon wafers. As a result, monocrystalline solar panels became more consistent in performance, with efficiencies reaching approximately 12–14%. However, due to higher production costs, their use was still limited compared to polycrystalline alternatives. In the 2000s and 2010s, significant advancements in solar cell design, including the introduction of Passivated Emitter and Rear Cell (PERC) technology and selective emitter structures, contributed to a notable increase in efficiency. By the mid-2010s, commercial monocrystalline modules were reaching efficiencies between 18% and 20%, gradually surpassing

polycrystalline panels in both performance and market share. From 2020 onward, the development of high-efficiency technologies such as PERC, TOPCon (Tunnel Oxide Passivated Contact), and heterojunction (HJT) cells further boosted the performance of monocrystalline panels. The adoption of n-type silicon, known for its reduced light-induced degradation and better carrier lifetime, has also enhanced long-term efficiency and reliability. Modern manufacturing techniques, including half-cut cell designs, multi-busbar (MBB) layouts, and bifacial modules, have helped raise commercial efficiencies to 22–23.7% [23].

Perovskite solar panels are a new generation of photovoltaic technology known for their high efficiency and low-cost potential. The term "perovskite" refers to a specific crystal structure, originally found in the mineral calcium titanium oxide (CaTiO_3), named after Russian scientist Lev Perovski in 1839. In solar cell applications, perovskites are typically hybrid organic-inorganic materials with the general formula ABX_3 , where:

- **A** is a cation such as methylammonium (MA^+), formamidinium (FA^+), or cesium (Cs^+),
- **B** is a metal cation, usually lead (Pb^{2+}) or tin (Sn^{2+}),
- **X** is a halide anion like iodide (I^-), bromide (Br^-), or chloride (Cl^-).

This structure allows perovskites to absorb light efficiently and convert it into electricity with remarkable effectiveness. Perovskite solar cells were first introduced in 2009 by Japanese scientist Tsutomu Miyasaka, achieving just 3.8% efficiency. In just over a decade, research and innovation have rapidly improved this figure. Today, single-junction perovskite cells exceed 25% efficiency, and tandem cells (combined with silicon) have reached over 30%. The rapid progress in perovskite research is due to their ease of fabrication, tunable properties, and compatibility with existing solar technologies. As development continues, perovskite solar panels are becoming a leading candidate for the next generation of affordable and efficient solar energy solutions [24].

Due to their lower production costs and rapidly increasing efficiency, perovskite solar panels are emerging as a strong alternative to traditional monocrystalline silicon panels. Their simpler manufacturing process and potential for high energy conversion make them highly competitive in both commercial and residential solar markets.

Feature	Monocrystalline Silicon	Perovskite Solar Cells
Efficiency	22-23.7%	24-30% (lab scale)
Stability	25+ years	5-10 years and improving
Cost	High	Low
Manufacturing	Energy-intensive	Low-cost, scalable
Environmental concern	Low	Moderate (due to lead)

Figure 5. Comparison Between Perovskite and Monocrystalline Solar Panels

The figure shows that in the next few years, perovskite solar cells have the potential to become a strong alternative to traditional silicon-based solar panels. One of the most promising features of perovskites is their high power conversion efficiency, which has rapidly increased in the last decade. While monocrystalline silicon panels have plateaued around 24-26% efficiency, perovskite-silicon tandem cells have already surpassed 30% in laboratory settings and continue to improve. Manufacturing perovskite panels is also less energy-intensive and more cost-effective. They can be produced using low-temperature, scalable methods such as inkjet printing or roll-to-roll processing. This could lead to cheaper solar solutions, particularly for lightweight or flexible applications like portable electronics, vehicles, or building-integrated photovoltaics.

However, the major barrier remains long-term stability. Silicon panels have proven durability over 25+ years, while perovskite materials are still undergoing improvements to withstand moisture, heat, and UV exposure. Research is advancing quickly, with some encapsulated perovskite cells showing promising lifetime results in controlled environments. If ongoing research succeeds in improving stability and scaling up production, perovskite panels could begin to replace or complement silicon in both residential and industrial applications within the next 5 to 10 years. Their potential to deliver higher efficiency at lower cost makes them one of the most exciting developments in solar technology today.

Electricity Demand in Uzbekistan: Uzbekistan's electricity demand has been steadily increasing due to rapid economic development, industrial expansion, and population growth. In 2024 alone, electricity production rose from 52.3 billion kWh to 54.43 billion kWh, reflecting a year-on-year increase of approximately 4.1%. Over the longer term, total electricity generation has grown by 38% between 2016 and 2024, reaching around 81.5 billion kWh. The country's annual electricity demand is projected to grow at an average rate of 7–8% through 2030. According to government forecasts, total consumption is expected to reach 117 billion kWh by 2030 and could climb to 121–135 billion kWh beyond 2035. This growth is fueled by both increased residential usage and the expansion of energy-intensive sectors such as manufacturing and infrastructure development. This is distributed as follows (figure 6).

Figure 6. Electricity production in Uzbekistan

To meet rising demand and enhance energy security, Uzbekistan is pursuing a strategy of diversification. This includes expanding its generation capacity from natural gas and hydro sources, while significantly increasing the share of renewable energy. The government aims to raise the contribution of renewables in electricity generation from 5% in 2024 to as much as 40–54% by 2030 [25].

In conclusion, currently, only about 5% of the electricity produced in Uzbekistan comes from renewable energy sources. Due to the country's rapidly growing population, declining underground resources, and increasing environmental challenges, there is a strong demand to raise this share. Given the limited availability of water resources and insufficient potential for wind power in many regions, solar panels naturally emerge as the most optimal solution. Therefore, efforts to implement affordable and high-efficiency solar panels are likely to prove effective and justified in the near future.

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